

**BENZOYL CHLORIDE AS A POLAR SOLVENT. PART I. SOLUBILITIES
OF SUBSTANCES AND THE FORMATION OF SOLVATES IN
BENZOYL CHLORIDE**

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A quantitative determination of the solubilities of various chlorides at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ and a qualitative one for a number of organic bases, oxides and other salts in benzoyl chloride have been carried out. Formation of solvates with this solvent has also been studied.

Benzoyl chloride, with its moderately high dielectric constant (22.9 at 25°) (Errara, *J. Phys. Radium*, 1924, 5, 309) and a convenient working range (m.p. -0.63° , b.p. 197°) is quite suitable for study as a non-aqueous solvent. As a knowledge of the solubilities of the various reactants and reaction products is necessary for this purpose, a quantitative determination of the solubilities of various chlorides at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ has been carried out, results of which are shown in Table I. The term 'insoluble' refers to a solubility of less than 0.1%.

TABLE I

Chloride.	Solubility (g./100 g. of solvent).	Colour.	Heat produced during mixing.
HgCl ₂	0.8	Light yellow	Nil
SnCl ₂	1.7	Reddish brown	Nil
SnCl ₄	Freely miscible	Faint red	Considerable
BiOCl	0.85	Colorless	"
BiCl ₃	1.56	"	Nil
AsCl ₃	Freely miscible	"	"
ZnCl ₂	0.1	"	"
SbOCl	13.03	Light brown	Appreciable
SbCl ₃	160.00	Dark brown	Heat absorbed
PCl ₃	Freely miscible	Colorless	Nil
POCl ₃	"	"	"
PSCl ₂	"	"	"
PCl ₅	2.2	"	"
SCl ₂	Freely miscible	Red	"
S ₂ Cl ₂	"	"	"
TeCl ₄	2.96	Light yellow	"
AlCl ₃	37.07	Dark brown	Appreciable
SOCl ₂	Freely miscible	Colorless	Nil
FeCl ₃	23.60	Dark brown	Appreciable

It has been observed that the strongly ionic compounds are practically insoluble in benzoyl chloride; thus, anhydrous chlorides of Hg^I, Na, K, Li, ammonium, Pb^{II}, Cd, Cu^{II}, Ag, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn, Ca, Ba and Sr are insoluble. The fact that benzoyl chloride has a comparatively low dielectric constant (cf. water, 81 at 18°) accounts for

* A preliminary note on the subject has already been published (*Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 28, 391).

its being a poor solvent for the strongly ionic compounds. The chlorides, which are soluble, are generally the Lewis acids, or are capable of producing the Lewis acids on dissolution. Most of them produce coloured solutions, probably due to the formation of complexes, and quite a few form solid solvates. Qualitative experiments have shown that the solubility of these chlorides increases with a rise in temperature.

The solubility of a number of oxides and salts has also been studied qualitatively (Table II). Most of these substances are solvolysed to produce chlorides (Part II of this series). The solubility of such compounds indirectly depends upon the solubility of the corresponding chlorides in this solvent.

TABLE II

* Fairly soluble.	Soluble with reaction. Sparingly soluble.	React to give insoluble chlorides.	Insoluble & unreactive
Fe ₂ O ₃	Ri ₂ O ₃	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃
Sb ₂ O ₃	HgO	PbO	Cr ₂ O ₃
Sb ₂ O ₅	MgO	CdO	TiO ₂
As ₂ O ₃	ZnO	CuO	P ₂ O ₅
[(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₅ , C ₇ H ₇]Cl	(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Hg	BaO	
(C ₆ H ₅ CO) ₂ O		AgNO ₃	
		NaNO ₂	
		KNO ₃	
		KBr	
		KI	
		CuCO ₃	
		CdCO ₃	

* The terms 'sparingly soluble' and 'fairly soluble' denote a solubility of less than 5% and 5-10% respectively.

A qualitative study of the solubility of organic bases like quinoline, pyridine, α - and β -picolines, dimethylaniline and diethylaniline has shown them to be appreciably soluble in benzoyl chloride and some of them form definite solvates with it.

Formation of Solvates.—The formation of monosolvates of aluminium chloride (Wilson and Fuller, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 406; Menshutkin, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 42, 1310), aluminium bromide (Menschutkin, *loc. cit.*; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1911, I, 481), gallium trichloride (Ulich and Heyne, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1941, B49, 284; Greenwood and Wade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1527), magnesium bromide (Menschutkin, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 39, 102), titanium tetrachloride (Cullinane, Chard and Leyshon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4106; Bertrand, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1880, 33, 403; 1881, 34, 631), ferric chloride (Nencki, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2414; Boeseken, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1903, 22, 315) and anhydrous sulphuric acid (Bergmann and Radt, *Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 1652) with benzoyl chloride has already been reported. In the present investigation, the formation of solvates by benzoyl chloride with other chlorides has been studied. An examination of the solid phase, obtained in the solubility determination in the case of each chloride, has shown that electrovalent compounds are resistant towards solvate formation. Thus, anhydrous chlorides of Na, K, Li, NH₄,

Hg^I, Pb^{II}, Ca, Ba, Sr, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd and Ag do not combine with benzoyl chloride. Bi^{III}, Sb^{III} and P^{III}, P^V, Se^{IV}, Te^{IV} and Hg^{II} chlorides also do not form any solvate with this solvent.

Manganese chloride forms a flesh coloured monosolvate, $MnCl_2 \cdot C_6H_5COCl$ which, decomposes without melting. Magnesium oxide gives a white monosolvate, $MgO \cdot C_6H_5COCl$. Seel (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1943, 252, 24) reported the formation of a monosolvate of antimony pentachloride with benzoyl chloride, while studying the solvent properties of liquid sulphur dioxide. This compound has now been prepared by the interaction of benzoyl chloride and antimony pentachloride directly.

A large amount of heat is produced when zinc oxide or cupric oxide reacts with benzoyl chloride. Though the ultimate products in these cases, at higher temperatures, are pure metal chlorides (Part II of the series), an examination of the solid phase, obtained during the determination of the solubility of these substances at 30°, shows the formation of intermediate solvates, e.g., $2 ZnCl_2 \cdot 3 (ZnO \cdot 2 C_6H_5COCl)$ and $3 CuCl_2 \cdot CuO \cdot C_6H_5COCl$ respectively.

Ferric oxide, chromium oxide, aluminium oxide, cadmium oxide, lead oxide (PbO), titanium dioxide, arsenious oxide and phosphorus pentoxide do not form any solvate with this solvent.

Formation of a monosolvate of pyridine with benzoyl chloride has been reported by Adkins and Thompson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2242). Now quinoline also has been found to form a white crystalline disolvate, $C_9H_7N \cdot 2C_6H_5COCl$, when both the liquids are mixed together.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzoyl chloride used in the present investigation was purified by collecting the distillate between 194° and 196°. This was again fractionated over dry magnesium oxide and the fraction distilling at 195°/740 mm was collected. Since benzoyl chloride is readily hydrolysed, carefully dried anhydrous substances have been used and their purity and anhydrous state checked by analysis.

Procedure.—A requisite quantity of the metal chloride along with benzoyl chloride (10-15 c.c.) was sealed in a dry ampoule, which was rotated in the thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ for about 48 hours to allow the mixture to attain equilibrium. The ampoule was then broken and the slurry was filtered quickly through a sintered glass funnel in a dry atmosphere. The solid was examined for the formation of solvates, while the solubility of the substance was determined by actual estimation of the cation from the filtrate (saturated solution) by the usual methods.

For the study of solvate formation, the solid phase was washed with benzoyl chloride and petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) successively and dried under vacuum. It was then analysed for the metal and chlorine and the formation of the solvates inferred.

In the case of the solvate of quinoline, the base was estimated by the Jackson and Smith method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 544). The results of analyses are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Solvate.		Found.	Calc.
$MnCl_2 \cdot C_6H_5COCl$	Mn :	21.54	20.58
	Cl :	40.94	39.94
$MgO \cdot C_6H_5COCl$	Mg :	13.20	13.46
	Cl :	19.83	19.63
$SbCl_5 \cdot C_6H_5COCl$	Sb :	27.70	27.69
	Cl :	48.52	48.43
2 ZnCl ₂ · 3 (ZnO · 2C ₆ H ₅ COCl)	Zn :	23.70	24.00
	Cl :	25.85	26.15
3 CuCl ₂ · CuO · C ₆ H ₅ COCl	Cu :	40.48	40.85
	Cl :	39.85	39.92
$C_9H_7N \cdot 2C_6H_5COCl$	Cl :	17.21	17.32
	N :	3.36	3.41

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Received April 7, 1958.